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Research Article

**CLINICAL AND DEMOGRAPHICAL ASSESSMENT OF
PEDIATRIC PATIENTS SUFFERING WITH FEBRILE ATTACK
AND TO EXAMINE THEIR ETIOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION**¹Dr Hafsa Naseer, ²Dr Sadia Shafique, ³Dr M. Suhaib Naeem¹Madina Teaching Hospital, ²Abbas Institute of Medical Sciences, ³Madina Teaching Hospital**Abstract**

This imminent research study was organized in Services Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan. The time duration of this research study was from January 2017 to December 2017. Total 100 children were selected for this study. The number of male and female was 68 (68 %) and 32 (32 %) respectively. 22.58 ± 12.50 months, was the mean age of participants. These children were suffering with febrile attack. The objective of this research study was clinical and demographical assessment of pediatric patients and to examine their etiological description. A Performa was outlined in order to assemble data of the patient. Out of 100 children, normal attack was observed in 78 (78 %) patients. 17.68 ± 12.09 hours was the mean duration of time between the start of fever and incidence of attacks. Anemia, malnutrition and high count of leukocyte were reported in 77 (77 %), 64 (64 %) and 51 (51 %) patients respectively. However, the most obvious reason of FS was serious respiratory infection, found in 72(72 %).

Key words: Anaemia, Pakistan, Febrile seizures, Aetiology, Age, Type.

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INTRODUCTION:

The pediatric patients are admitted to the emergency wards of hospital most commonly due to Febrile attack (FS) [1]. About 2 – 5 of all young children are influenced by it [2]. In Asian countries, there is high prevalence of FS. In these countries, the incidence of infections is higher in young age according to history of FS [3]. The definition of febrile seizure is given by the National Institute of Health (NIH) consent, according to NIH statement; FS is an incident of early childhood and connected with fever and its incidence is reported between 3 months to five years of age. The causes of attack are uncertain. The definition of FS is also provided by the International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE). It states that FS is an attack which is related to febrile fever in the absence of acute electrolyte imbalance or absence of infection of central nervous system (CNS). Usually, there are two categories of FS. One of them is simple febrile seizures (SFS) and the other is complex FS (CFS).

There exist a third category of FS which is not very common. It is known as febrile seizure epileptics. In this category, without any neurological reclamation, the timings of attack are more than half an hour. The proper causes that lead to this disorder are still undiscovered. In the diagnosis of FS, many factors are involved. These factors include family background [3], infections related to virus and bacteria [4], vaccinations [5], insufficient zinc and iron [6], timing period of breast feeding, use of alcohol / smoking, sudden changes in body temperature and gender. Many environmental and genetic factors also lead to febrile seizure. In different regions of globe, there exists a variation in constant rate of FS. Family background of patients with febrile attack and low fever at first attack are responsible for recurrence rate of FS. The objective of the present study was clinical and demographical assessment of patients and to examine their etiological description.

METHODS AND RESULTS:

This imminent research study was organized in Services Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan. The time

duration of this study was from January 2017 to December 2017.

Total patients enrolled for this study were 100. The sample was assembled through regular sampling technique. Socio – economic standard, living place, gender and race was not considered during sampling. A Performa was signed which was approved by institutional ethical committee. Through this Performa, information regarding patients was assembled. If the attack lasts for more than 15 minutes and central activity is observed in the start or during poetical period and if the attack repeats itself in the period of 24 hours, it is termed as CFS. Whereas, if time period of attack is 15 minutes and if doesn't occur during 24 hours and if no central manifestations are observed, it is called an SFS.

The patients selected for this research study were suffering with FS. The age of these patients was between 3 – 72 months. Those children who were observed with known cases of chronic disorders, known cases of inborn mistakes, febrile attacks, infections of CNS, electrolyte imbalance and with age < 3 months or > 72 months were struck off from research study. According to Gomez classification, patients were checked for the nutritional status [7]. SPSS version 17 was employed for assessment of data. For quantitative variables such as age, mean and standard deviation (SD) were measured. Whereas, for qualitative variables, the measurement was made for percentage and frequency. The value of P was <0.05 which was valuable.

The number of male and females out of 100 cases was 68(68 %) and 32(32 %) respectively. 1.4: 1 was the ratio recorded for male to female. The mean age of these patients was 22.58 ± 12.50 months. Out of 100 patients, the age of 63 (63 %) patients was between 19 to 24 months. One event of attack during the illness was observed in 65 (65%) cases. The background of 30(30%) cases was not found with FS. In different patients, different causes were observed. The common causes of FS were anemia and ARI in 77 (77 %) and 72 (72 %) causes respectively. The simple FS was observed in 78 (78 %) cases. On the other hand, the patients with attack between 13 – 24 hours were 54(54 %) (Table - 1).

Table No 01: Demographic profile.

Parameter	Frequency / Percentage
Gender	
Male	68
Female	32
Age in Months	
03-6M	01
07-12M	19
13-18M	16
9-24	27
25-30	15
31-36	09
37-48	03
49-60	07
61-72	03
Time in Hours (between onset of fever and seizure)	
<12hours	27
12-24	54
25-36	04
37-48	10
>48	05
Aetiology of fever	Raised
ARI	72
AGE	12
Malaria	03
Otitis media	04
Enteric fever	02
UTI	07
Seizure type	
Simple	78
Complex	22
Family History	
Nil	70
Present	30
Episode of Seizure	
One (Single)	65
Recurrence	35
Nutritional Status	
Well nourished	36
Malnourished	64
Anaemia confirmed by investigating	
Present	77
Absent	23
TLC on investigation	
Normal	40
Abnormal	60

The valuable variables observed were family background, age, cause and anemia ($P < 0.05$ each). Along with various variables, type of attack was compared statistically. (Table – 2).

Table No 02: Statistical comparison of seizure type with various variables.

Variable	Simple	Complex	P – Value
Gender			
Male	53	15	
Female	25	07	0.983
Age			
3-6 Months	01	00	
7-12 Months	18	01	
3-18 Months	16	00	
19-24 Months	16	11	
25-30 Months	15	00	
31-36 Months	05	04	
3.1-4 Years	02	01	
4.1-5 Years	04	03	
>5 Years	01	02	0.000
Family History			
Nil	61	09	
Yes	17	13	0.001
Episode of Seizure			
One (Single)	58	07	
Recurrence	20	15	0.001
Aetiology			
ARI	61	11	
AGE	12	00	
Malaria	02	01	
Otitis media	02	02	
Enteric fever	00	02	
UTI	01	06	0.000
Nutritional Status			
Well nourished	31	05	
Malnourished	47	17	0.131
Anemia			
Nil	14	09	
Yes	64	13	0.031
TLC			
Normal	43	07	
Raised	35	15	0.128

DISCUSSION:

With many other research studies, the mean age of initial attack, as reported in our research study, was comparable [6,7,8,9]. Many other research studies were also organized. Our results are comparable with these studies. They showed that FS usually comes with initial 24 hours [10].

Patients were examined for nutritional status. Majority of the patients were found with malnutrition. In another study [11], the association of FS with malnutrition was not valuable. The reasons of FS pointed out in our study were similar with the studies conducted earlier [12,13,14]. In our study, majority of the patients had initial event of attack. This is also comparable with previous research studies [13]. The types of FS, examined in this study are convenient with the history [15,16].

CONCLUSION:

In this study, most of the patients were males. These were suffering with simple FS, first event of attack and had initial 24 hours of illness. Different factors that contribute to FS were high TLC, malnutrition and anemia. To examine the relationship of FS with infections of bacteria and malnutrition, more studies should be organized.

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